

Experimental study

Antimicrobial Properties of Plants: Uncovering the Potential of Olive Leaves from Portuguese Cultivars.

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Abstract

Background: Complementary therapies in health, such as functional nutrition and phytotherapy, have recently grown, especially under the knowledge diaspora of the Oriental herbal medicine. This shift is also driven by the emerging economic paradigm, which moves from a linear to a circular model, where plant by-products from the primary sector are upcycled into a wide range of value-added products, particularly for therapeutic applications. Different western plant parts, including olive leaves, have been consumed as extract, infusion or as a whole herbal powder with several health benefits. **Objective:** This study assessed the antimicrobial potential against some Gram (+) and Gram (-) bacteria by olive leaves extracts from three different Portuguese cultivars - Cobrançosa, Madural, and Verdeal - randomly mixed cultivated in an olive grove located in Vale de Salgueiros (Portugal). **Methods:** The antimicrobial activity of the olive tree leaf extracts was measured for Gram (+) *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *B. cereus* and Gram (-) *P. aeruginosa*, *Salmonella Enteritidis*, and *E. coli* by agar diffusion assay. **Results:** All cultivars displayed antimicrobial activity against Gram (-) *P. aeruginosa*, *Salmonella enteritidis* and Gram (+) *B. cereus*. Only Verdeal cultivar showed activity against Gram (+) *S. aureus*, and none presented a significant result against Gram (+) *S. epidermidis* nor Gram (-) *E. coli*. **Conclusions:** Overall, *O. europaea* leaves from Portuguese cultivars showed effective antimicrobial activity against prevalent bacterial strains, suggesting their applicability in therapeutic formulations for human and veterinary use, as well as a natural preservative agent in food and cosmetic products.

Keywords: Western Plants; *O. europaea* L. folium; Portuguese Cultivars; Therapeutic properties; Antimicrobial activity.

Citation: de Oliveira N., Criado M.B., Machado J., Chéu M.H., Lopes L., Barroso M.F., Silva A., Sousa S., Domingues V., Grosso C. Antimicrobial Properties of Plants: Uncovering the Potential of Olive Leaves from Portuguese Cultivars. Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health. 2025;3(2) 10.5281/zenodo.16814258

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 30 July 2025

Reviewed: 10 August 2025

Accepted: 11 August 2025

Published: 12 August 2025

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Complementary therapies in health, such as functional nutrition and phytotherapy, have recently grown, especially under the knowledge diaspora of the Oriental herbal medicine ^{1,2}. For this, also contributes the latest economic paradigm of transitioning from linear to circular model, wherein plant by-products generated from the primary sector are upcycled into diversified traded products, namely of therapeutic use ^{3,4}. Different western plant parts, including olive leaves, have been consumed as extract, infusion or as a whole

herbal powder for numerous health matters ^{5,6}. Several benefits and applications have been associated with the bioactive compounds found in olive leaves, and substantial compositional differences have been found amongst diverse *O. europaea* L. *folium* cultivars. This differentiation regards not only qualitative and quantitative characterisation of polyphenols but also overall nutritional composition, vitamin E, fatty acids (FAs), as well as antioxidant and antimicrobial activity ^{4,5,7-9}. Several authors found a correlation between the composition of olive leaves and features such as air temperature and precipitation levels along seasons, type of soil, cultivation techniques and soil supplementation, as well as type of cultivar ⁵. It has been consensual that the same cultivar brought up in assorted environments also displays biochemical diversity, reflecting a differential in their industrial and therapeutic applications. Mirandela (MIR) and Valpaços (VAL) in Northeast Portugal have extensive olive groves of autochthonous olive cultivars, known for their premium Protected Designation of Origin olive oil, mainly produced with Cobrançosa, Madural and Verdeal cultivars ^{5,7-9}. Recent leaf characterisation studies of these three cultivars confirm a biochemical diversity between plants cultivated in MIR and VAL ^{5,7-9}. MIR olive leaves revealed high levels of total phenolic content (TPC) and lipidic content with high levels of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) and a small ω -6/ ω -3 ratio ⁷⁻⁹. These characteristics may render MIR's olive leaves as a highly beneficial antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial, highly renewable, natural resource. Pereira *et al.* ¹⁰ already tested the phenolic composition and the antimicrobial power of an aqueous leaf extract of *O. europaea* Cobrançosa, obtained from an olive grove in Mirandela in November 2014. The highest level of growth inhibition among all tested concentrations in that study was observed at 5 mg/mL. Although no lethal behaviour was detected, a notable inhibitory activity was recorded against *B. cereus* CECT 148, *B. subtilis* CECT 498, *S. aureus* ESA 7, *E. coli* CECT 101, *P. aeruginosa* CECT 108, and *K. pneumoniae* ESA 8. Authors also reported that the high concentration of oleuropein, followed by other phenolic compounds, such as flavonoids luteolin-7-O-glucoside and apigenine-7-O-glucoside, might contribute to this antimicrobial effect ¹⁰. It is known that, on one hand, a higher grade of inflammation has been associated with Gram (-) rather than Gram (+) bacteria ⁹ raising a concern regarding the treatment of Gram (-) sepsis. On the other hand, it is known that Gram (+) bacteria contribute *circa* 76% of infections in health-compromised individuals, whereas Gram (-) microorganisms only represent 14% of these infections ⁹. Moreover, multidrug-resistant (MDR) microorganisms such as *B. cereus*, *S. aureus*, and *E. coli* demand searching for alternative solutions to the overuse of antibiotics. For its broad antimicrobial activity, plant derivatives such as olive leaf extracts (OLEs) have regarded as a privileged nature-based source for designing pharmacological actives.

1.2. Objective

Therefore, this study aimed to assess the polyphenolic content and antimicrobial activity of the hydroethanolic extracts of three Portuguese cultivars' leaves (Cobrançosa, Madural and Verdeal) from the MIR olive grove. In this olive grove, (coordinates in WGS84: Lat: 41.579700 and Long: -7.241642) these different varieties have been cultivated randomly mixed in the same geographical space for over 60 years, embedded in a total area of 13.5 ha, equivalently distributed: (1) 59.26% (8.0 ha) of *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa, (2) 10.37% (1.4 ha) of *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural, and (3) 30.37% (4.1 ha) of *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal cultivars. The allocation of olive trees/area is around 200 items/49m², being even denser in topographical planes. The maintenance of this olive grove includes conventional cultivation techniques with application of (1) CaSO₄ (2) Sprintplus[®] (algae-based), and (3) organic fertiliser with soil reviver. Trees are biannually pruned after the olive harvest season.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Olive leaves extracts

The samples for phytochemical analysis were obtained by subjecting 0.60 g of powdered olive leaves from each cultivar to an organic extraction with 12 mL of a hydroethanolic mixture (50/50, v/v) for 60 min at 55 °C.

2.2. Phenolic and Flavonoid content assessment

Both Total Phenolic Content (TPC) and Total Flavonoid Content (TFC) values were determined via colourimetric assays based on Folin–Ciocalteu reagent according to a previous procedure⁹. Calibration curves for TPC were calculated using gallic acid (GA), and for TFC were prepared with epicatechin, and the results were expressed as milligrams of epicatechin equivalent (ECE) per gram of sample. The phenolic profile was identified through High-Performance Liquid Chromatography according to a previous protocol⁹.

2.3. Antimicrobial Activity

Microorganisms and Culture Conditions

The antimicrobial activity of the olive tree leaf extracts was assessed against Gram-positive bacterial strains: *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (NCTC 11047) and *Bacillus cereus* (ATCC 14579); and Gram-negative strains: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145), *Salmonella Enteritidis* (ATCC 13076) and *Escherichia coli* (NCTC 9001). Aliquots from each culture were transferred to fresh MHB and properly diluted to an optical density of 0.09–0.11, corresponding to the 0.5 MacFarland standard, to reach $1\text{--}2 \times 10^8$ colony formation units (CFUs).

Agar Diffusion Assay

Assays followed the adapted protocol from the CLSI guidelines¹¹: 100 µL of microbial suspensions were seeded and spread into Petri dishes containing Mueller–Hinton II agar, divided into sections - 15 µL of each tested extract (test section), DMSO (negative control section), and 40% lactic acid (positive control section) to incubate at 37°C for 24h (Figure 1). Growth inhibition was quantified, in triplicate, by diameter measurement of inhibition circular zones.

Figure 1: Petri Dish Model incubated at 37°C for 24h. Description: A - OLE 20mg/mL. B- Negative Control (DMSO); C - Positive Control (40% Acid Lactic).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Phenolic Content

Literature evokes polyphenols as the main bioactives in the treatment of several health conditions, acting as anti-inflammatory, immunoprotective and antimicrobial agents⁵. Overall, MIR's OLE presented a phenolic prolife ranging from 37.90 mgGAE/g dry weight to 53.90 mgGAE/g dry weight (Figure 2).

Figure 2: TPC and TFC of a fresh sample of olive leaf extracts from three Portuguese cultivars harvested in Mirandela grove.

Despite *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural’s extracts presenting the absolute top weight of hydroxytyrosol (HT) 10.86 mg/g of dried extract (Figure 3), each gram of *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal’s extract was relatively richer in HT (46.12%) than other compounds (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Absolute composition of identified phenol compounds in the hydroethanolic olive leaf extracts of three Portuguese cultivars expressed in mg/g of dried extract.

Figure 4: Relative content of identified phenolic compounds in the hydroethanolic olive leaf extracts of Portuguese cultivars expressed in percentage (%) phenolic compound/g of dried extract.

O. europaea L. var *europaea* Verdeal's leaf extract showed a relatively higher TPC level associated with a lower level of water content (data not shown), suggesting potential for obtaining high-quality polyphenols. On the other hand, *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal's leaves also showed the lowest level of protein and the highest Arsenicum (As) content among the three selected cultivars (data not shown), which makes *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural a safer substrate for polyphenols. Some studies evidenced an immunoprotection and antimicrobial action of phenolic compounds such as OLEP, TY, and HT^{5,9}, wherein their anti-Gram (+) and anti-Gram (-) most studied effect is membrane disruption⁹. The hydroxyl groups in phenolics steer electron delocalisation, playing as proton exchangers, inducing the cell's membrane disruption and so, bacterial death⁹. Among the several identified single phenolic compounds in the OLEs, HT was the predominant compound for all cultivars (Figures 2 and 3). HT is referred to in literature as the primary compound responsible for the bio-activity of oleuropein (OLEP), mainly because of its high antioxidant properties, but also an immuno-protective and antimicrobial action^{5,7,9}. Other phenolic compounds have shown antibacterial activity *in vitro* against several bacterial strains responsible for intestinal and respiratory infections^{5,9,10}. These compounds also showed promising potential as preservatives in the food industry^{5,9}, particularly due to their ability to inhibit the growth of *Helicobacter pylori*, a bacterium associated with peptic ulcers and gastric cancer¹². OLE polyphenols have also revealed antiviral and antiprotozoal activities¹³. This wide antimicrobial range makes OLEs an easily available reservoir for designing pharmacological actives. In this sense, silver nanoparticles/attapulgitite nanocomposites using an OLE confirmed the ability of olive leaf waste to be valorised into a biotechnological asset to target MDR bacteria, reaching inhibition at higher concentrations (100 µg/mL)^{5,9}. The phenolic profile assessed in the present study showed that besides HT, flavonoids are also prominent, with an accumulated total very close for both *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa and Madural, surpassing the relative percentage of HT in these OLEs (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Phenolic relative composition (%) phenolic compound/g of OLE dried, hydroethanolic extract, with accumulated flavonoid percentual in hydroethanolic OLE of three Portuguese cultivars.

O. europaea L. var *europaea* Verdeal's extract revealed a slightly different profile compared to the other extracts, following the waning order of HT > apigenin derivative > luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside > verbascoside > apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside (Figures 3 and 4). Interestingly, it was reported that luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and verbascoside exhibit antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* ⁹, speculating a possible differential positive activity of the *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal extract against this microbial. Also, the flavone apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside was found to be higher in both *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa and Madural extracts (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Relative flavonoid composition (%) of phenolic compound/g of dried hydroethanolic OLE extract of three Portuguese cultivars.

A previous work ¹⁰ reported a different phenolic profile for MIR *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa leaf; however, these authors used an aqueous extract and leaves were harvested in November (Figure 7).

Figure 7: A. Phenolic profile of MIR *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa aqueous leaf extract with harvest in November based on data of Pereira *et al.* ¹⁰ (relative% % of phenolic compound per Kg of olive leaf lyophilised extract). B. Discrimination of the phenolic class represented by percentage per Kg of lyophilised extract, based on data of Pereira *et al.*, 2007 ¹⁰.

This aqueous extract showed a predominance of Oleuropein> Luteolin-7-O-glucoside> apigenin-7-O-glucoside. The percentages of these flavones didn't vary much between the aqueous and our hydroethanolic extract, indicating a stronger influence of the harvesting season than the extraction solvent in the phenolic profile. Still, the aqueous extracts showed inhibitory action against most tested microorganisms at low concentrations, such as 5mg/mL ¹⁰.

3.2. Antimicrobial Activity

Diluted extracts (20mg/mL) achieved an overall wider inhibition spectrum. *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal was the only one to show activity against *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) (Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8: Antimicrobial activity of olive leaf extracts from three Portuguese cultivars against selected Gram (+) and Gram (-) bacteria, measured by diameter of growth inhibition (mm).

Figure 9: Relative microbial inhibition by olive leaf hydroethanolic extracts compared to the positive control expressed in percentage (%).

All extracts exhibited antimicrobial activity against Gram (+) *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579), Gram (-) *Salmonella* Enteritidis (ATCC 13076) and *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) (Figures 8 and 9). No trace of activity was found against Gram (+) *S. epidermidis* (NCTC 11047) and Gram (-) *E. coli* (NCTC 9001) (Figures 8 and 9). Despite an overall broader activity against Gram (-) strains, both *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal and Cobrançosa extracts attained higher growth inhibition against two distinct Gram (+) strains. Regarding the antimicrobial effect, using as reference the positive control, we can point out:

- *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal showed an antimicrobial efficacy against: *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) > *Salmonella* Enteritidis (ATCC 13076) > *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579) > *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145), with relative inhibition values of 78.90%, 66.79%, 61.25% and 59.93%, respectively (Figures 9 and 10).
- *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa acted against: *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579) > *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) > *Salmonella* Enteritidis (ATCC 13076), with relative inhibition values of 71.44%, 66.06% and 60.99%, respectively (Figures 9 and 10).
- *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural showed antimicrobial activity against: *Salmonella* Enteritidis (ATCC 13076) > *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) > *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579), with relative inhibition values of 71.38%, 57.95% and 57.93%, respectively (Figures 9 and 10).

The differential behaviour found for each OLE might be intrinsically related to their specific phenolic composition, as was referred to in the literature. For that, it was developed a synthetic visual representation was developed comparing the antimicrobial behaviour of the three studied hydroethanolic OLE (Figure 10) and their respective phenolic architectural profile (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Spatial distribution of the overall antimicrobial activity by the hydroethanolic OLE of three Portuguese cultivars.

Figure 11: Spatial distribution of the overall phenolic constitution by the hydroethanolic OLE of three Portuguese cultivars.

In general, a closer profile was found between the antimicrobial action of the OLE from Cobrançosa and Madural cultivars and also for their respective phenolic composition (Figures 10 and 11). *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal extracts were the sole to act against *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) with an inhibition of *circa* 78.90% relative to the positive control (Figures 8, 9 and 10). The OLE from this cultivar showed the higher relative content of HT, followed by *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural, whose prominent action was displayed against *Salmonella* Enteritidis (Figures 8, 9 and 10), but the HT content alone seems to be insufficient to explain the antimicrobial behaviour of *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal against *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) as well as that of *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural against *Salmonella* Enteritidis (ATCC 13076). Furthermore, as it is shown in Figure 2, these two OLEs were identified with the highest values of TPC, and so an assorted

type of additive or synergetic effects may deliver these differential results. Literature mentions the action of flavonoids, including luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and verbascoside against *S. aureus*⁹, as well as hydroxytyrosol¹⁴, in synergy with ampicillin¹⁵. Besides luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, other OLE phenolic secondary metabolites showed additive effects against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*¹⁵. These results were not observed here, probably because the OLE concentration (20mg/mL) might not be enough to achieve the desired effect. Other authors referred inhibition of *E. coli* at higher concentrations, such as 62.5 mg/mL¹⁶.

O. europaea L. var *europaea* Madural's extract achieved higher efficacy against Gram (-) *Salmonella* Enteritidis (ATCC 13076), with a relative inhibition of 71.38% (Figures 9 and 10), followed by very close results against Gram (-) *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) and Gram (+) *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579) with relative inhibitions of 57.95% and 57.93%, respectively (Figures 9 and 10). On the other hand, *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa's cultivar inhibited mostly Gram (+) *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579), showing about 71.44% relative inhibition, followed by Gram (-) *P. aeruginosa* and *Salmonella* Enteritidis with relative microbial growth inhibition of 66.06% and 60.99%, respectively (Figures 9 and 10). Despite their closer phenolic profile (Figure 11), flavones apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside, apigenin derivatives and verbascoside were found in higher concentration in *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa extract (Figures 3, 4 and 11), whereas HT and luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside were found at slightly higher values in *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural (Figures 3, 4 and 11), which could explain their differential antimicrobial properties. On the other hand, the OLE from *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa also displayed a differential antimicrobial activity compared to the aqueous leaf extract from this cultivar harvested in MIR in 2004 by Pereira *et al.*¹⁰. These authors found inhibition of all the tested bacteria and fungi, suggesting a broad antimicrobial activity of olive leaf extracts in a concentration-dependent manner¹⁰, with an inhibition of growth against: *B. cereus* ~ *C. albicans* > *E. coli* > *S. aureus* > *C. neoformans* ~ *K. pneumoniae* ~ *P. aeruginosa* > *B. subtilis*¹⁰. In the study of Pereira *et al.*, it was also found IC₂₅ values of 0.63mg/mL, 1.81 mg/mL, 2.68 mg/mL and 3.22 mg/mL for *B. cereus*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*, respectively. This behavioural difference between these two leaf extracts of the same cultivar might derive from a diversified biochemical architecture influenced by: harvest in another season, varied agricultural practice (including genetic variation by crossed pollination due to other cultivars' vicinity), but also by different extraction solvent polarity.

Knowing that polyphenols are responsible for antioxidant action, which is also linked to antimicrobial behaviour, we compared the antioxidant activity of the three cultivars' extracts analysed in this study. Alike their phenolic and antimicrobial action profiles, these extracts also displayed a distinguished antioxidant behaviour among three different tests - DPPH, FRAP and NO inhibition: *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa displayed higher DPPH radical scavenging activity (around 1.3 x more than *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural and 3.1 x more than *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal, data not shown); *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural, exhibited reduced antioxidant power (around 1.1 x more than *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal and Cobrançosa, data not shown); *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Verdeal displayed a slightly higher NO scavenging activity (1.5x more than *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa and 1.9 more than *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madural, data not shown). This divergence in the antioxidant behaviour might indicate that the phenolic profile *per se* isn't enough to justify the OLE antimicrobial behaviour. Literature also refers to the antimicrobial action of FAs, though disruption of the electron transport chain, cell lysis, inhibition of nutrient uptake, and cell deactivation⁹, disrupting quorum sensing, horizontal gene transfer, metabolic routes and nucleic acid reproduction¹⁷, stating that FA unsaturation and carbon-length chain affect FA's antimicrobial activity¹⁷. In this sense, our extracts from *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Cobrançosa and Verdeal showed higher ΣMUFAs (data not shown), which could mean some additive/synergetic action with phenolic content against *B. cereus*, for example, and *O. europaea* L. var *europaea* Madu-

ral and Verdeal extracts had higher Σ PUFAs, which could mark a differential against *Salmonella Enteritidis*. Overall, our results bring forward a panoply of compounds that might be acting in an additive/synergetic mode to deliver a valuable differentiated antimicrobial behaviour by the studied OLEs. To better understand which specific compounds and molecular mechanisms could be associated with the displayed behaviour, further multivariate statistical procedures, such as Principal Component Analysis, should be performed upon the experimental results.

4. Conclusions

All tested extracts (Cobrançosa, Madural, and Verdeal) from Mirandela showed antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579) and Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) and *Salmonella Enteritidis*. Only the Verdeal cultivar extract was effective against *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923), and none of the extracts were effective against *S. epidermidis* or *E. coli*. Each cultivar demonstrated a specific antimicrobial inhibition profile: Verdeal - highest efficacy against *S. aureus*; Cobrançosa - strongest inhibition of *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579); and Madural: best performance against *Salmonella Enteritidis* (ATCC 13076). These differences can be associated with variations in phenolic composition. However, the data suggest that synergistic effects between phenolic compounds better explain the antimicrobial activity differences. Unsaturated fatty acid composition and antioxidant activity may also play a role. From the results obtained, we can conclude that the Portuguese olive leaf extracts studied show significant potential for therapeutic use, including: human and veterinary phytotherapeutic formulations, natural preservatives for the food and cosmetics industries and development of green nanocomposites, such as silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), for targeted antimicrobial applications. *O. europaea* L. var. *europaea* Verdeal's leaf extracts presented the most adequate matrix for producing green AgNPs against Gram (+) *S. aureus*. The leaf extracts of *Olea europaea* L. var. *europaea* Cobrançosa demonstrated greater potential for incorporation into green nanocomposites targeting Gram (+) *B. cereus* and Gram (-) *P. aeruginosa*. In contrast, the extracts from *Olea europaea* L. var. *europaea* Madural appeared more suitable for the development of NCs aimed at combating Gram (-) *Salmonella Enteritidis*. Further studies are needed to test higher extract concentrations, different extraction methods, and perform advanced statistical analysis (e.g., Principal Component Analysis) to better understand the underlying mechanisms. Additional research should also explore the synergistic potential of combining extracts from different cultivars and assess effects against more resistant strains. This study highlights the therapeutic and economic potential of olive leaf extracts from Portuguese cultivars and represents a scientific and practical valorisation of a natural resource with promising cross-sectoral applications. Olive leaves could symbolize hope embodied in nature for their diversified array of successful applications whether in pharmaceutical, cosmetic or food industry mirroring a model of sustainable circular economy inspired in the natural cycles themselves where it is possible to apply the words of the chemist Antoine-Laurent de Lavoisier (1743 -1794): nothing is lost, nothing is created, everything is transformed.

Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 2nd International Congress on Complementary Therapies in Health, held on 28 June 2025.

The authors show their gratitude to the farm owners from Vale de Salgueiros, Mirandela region, who made it possible to access samples of three Portuguese variants of olive leaf for analysis in the present study. Also, a word of gratitude to ICBAS, in particular to Professor Jorge Machado, for supporting the research and revival of homeland plant varieties as a push for local and sustainable economic development.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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